

“MICROSPONGE TECHNOLOGY: REVOLUTIONIZING CONTROLLED AND TOPICAL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS”

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Abstract

The microsp sponge drug delivery systems are the next generation of porous polymeric carrier systems used for the controlled and sustained release of drugs. The pore structure of these microsized sponge-like structures are interconnected, which can improve the drug stability, efficacy and patient compliance by trapping both hydrophilic and lipophilic drugs. Microsp sponge technology has attracted significant interest for pharmaceutical research due to a number of disadvantages of conventional topical and controlled-release formulation: burst drug release; skin irritation; low retention; and frequent doses. A number of preparation methods such as “quasi-emulsion solvent diffusion”, “suspension polymerization”, “double emulsion”, “oil-in-oil emulsification” and “lyophilization” have been used for the preparation of microsponges. Microsponges have various performance factors including polymer composition, pore size, particle size, drug-polymer interaction and environmental factors. Various characterization techniques such as SEM, FTIR, DSC, zeta potential analysis, encapsulation efficiency and in-vitro release studies are important to assess the quality of the formulation and release behavior. Topical, transdermal, oral, ocular and cosmetic drug delivery have been found to have promising application of microsp sponge systems for antifungal, anti-acne, anti-inflammatory, sunscreen and wound healing treatments, respectively. Recent developments are directed towards biodegradable polymers, stimuli-responsive systems and nanotechnology-based enhanced microsponges for targeted and sustained drug delivery systems. The review highlights the formulation strategies, mechanisms, characterization methods, therapeutic applications, current advancements and future prospects of microsp sponge drug delivery systems for modern pharmaceutics.

Keywords: Microsp sponge; Controlled drug delivery; Topical drug delivery; Porous polymeric systems; Sustained release; Quasi-emulsion solvent diffusion; Drug entrapment; Characterization; Novel drug delivery system; Pharmaceutical applications.

INTRODUCTION

Polymeric microsponges with porous structure are advanced carrier systems which are developed for controlled and topical drug delivery. They are small hollow beads (usually 5–300 µm) made of a cross-linked polymer like Eudragit, ethyl cellulose or polymethyl methacrylate. In the late 1980s Won introduced the concept of microsp sponge technology and it

was eventually patented for topical delivery applications. These systems aim to address the drawbacks of traditional creams, ointments and gels – including burst drug release, poor retention, skin irritation and frequent application. The porous structure and the large internal surface area of microsponges allow them to trap both lipophilic and hydrophilic drugs, and release drugs when stimulated by pressure, pH and temperature;^[1,5]

The polymeric composition of microsponges makes them suitable for a variety of advantages, including drug stability, drug release control, skin retention, reduced systemic absorption and patient compliance. They also exhibit excellent thermal stability, pH tolerance, high loading capacity, and tolerance for a wide variety of dosage forms such as gels, creams, powders etc., which has led to their extensive research for use in several therapeutic areas including the treatment of antifungal, anti-acne, anti-inflammatory, sunscreen and depigmenting agents, where the aim is to extend the duration of the activity of the drug, and to reduce its irritation [6,7].

The ideal microsphere system should have uniform particle size, structural integrity, controlled porosity, good drug entrapment efficiency, chemical stability and compatibility with polymers and excipients. The particles should be stable throughout formulation and application and should have a consistent and predictable release of the drug [3, 8].

Fig no.1 structure of microsponges

ADVANTAGES

The use of microsponges has several benefits based upon their porous structure and their controlled release. Have good thermal stability and are stable over a wide pH range, suitable for a wide range of formulation conditions. Microsponges can provide a high drug loading efficiency, prolonged drug release, skin retention and patient compliance. They also decrease the number of doses needed, minimise local irritation and side effects, increase moisture stability and may increase bioavailability due to decreased first-pass metabolism. The above properties made Microsponges very beneficial in the Controlled/Topical Drug Delivery System (CDDS) [8,3,25,30].

LIMITATIONS

During the preparation of microsphere, sometimes it is necessary to use organic solvents, which can be flammable and harmful to the environment. Often residual solvents, monomers

or unreacted polymer remain in the product that can be toxic or have biocompatibility problems. So, solvent selection, purification methods and regulatory aspects are important in the formulation of microsp sponge, which should ensure the safety and stability of formulation [3,8,25,30].

The following properties would be suitable for microsponges.

Microsponges may possess some of the following structural and physicochemical properties which are desirable for them to be used as drug carriers:

Structural Integrity: Spherical architecture should not have to collapse during formulation or application.

Controlled solubility: Desirable is limited solubility and water immiscible is a plus for a controlled release.

Chemical stability: Microsponges should not react with polymers, and should be stable during processing.

They should be inert to monomers and the viscosity should not change during preparation of the formulation.

Not too great an addition of viscosity to the mixture should take place during their preparation as this would affect the ease of the processing.

Optimum particle size: The size of the particles recommended by the literature is 5-300 μm in diameter, which can provide uniformity, effective encapsulation or controlled release [3,8,25,30].

The factors affecting the release of the drug from these microsp sponge.

The composition of the polymer, pore size, solubility of the drug, the diffusion characteristics and the environment are reported to influence the drug release from microsponges. The drug-polymer interface and surrounding medium have an important role in the control of the release pattern. The porous microsp sponge structure can also be affected by external factors, including temperature, pH, friction and pressure, and affect drug diffusion back into the microsp sponge. The drug release can be improved by increasing the temperature and rubbing the system and under some conditions, pH-sensitive systems can provide controlled drug release. Various methods have been applied for the study of microsp sponge formulations such as FTIR, DSC, PXRD, SEM and HPLC [9,28,29]. The release of entrapped drug with several factor is increased as shown in figure.

Fig.2 factors affecting release of drug from microsp sponge formulation.^[47]

METHODS OF PREPERATION OF MICROSPONGES

The quasi-emulsion solvent diffusion method

It is a good method to prepare microsponges that is uniform and high entrapment efficiency. This involves dissolving a polymer like Eudragit RS 100 or ethyl cellulose or eudragit L 100 in a volatile solvent (e.g., ethyl alcohol). Organic phase is used to incorporate the drug through ultrasonication to achieve proper dispersion and plasticizers are added to impart flexibility and stability. An aqueous solution of PVA is continuously stirred with this internal phase being added slowly. Due to the diffusion of solvents, quasi emulsion droplets are formed, which are then solidified to form porous microsponges. The end products are collected, washed and then oven dried at 40°C for 12 hours.^[10]

Fig.3 Quasi emulsion solvent diffusion method.^[47]

Liquid-Liquid Suspension Polymerization

The one step process is the dissolution of immiscible monomers along with the active pharmaceutical ingredient in an appropriate solvent and dispersal into an aqueous phase

containing surfactants and suspending agents. The polymerization is catalysed, heated or irradiated to form spherical porous microsponges. After polymerization, solid particles are separated, washed and dried to get the final microsphere product. [8]

Fig.4 Liquid liquid suspension polymerization^[47]

Incorporation of Porogens

The use of porogenic agents is a commonly used method to improve the porosity of microsphere structures. Hydrogen peroxide or sodium bicarbonate is some of the more common porogens that are added to the formulation's internal phase. These agents are scattered in the polymeric solution to create an even distribution, and then re-emulsified in an aqueous phase of polyvinyl alcohol (PVA). One of the processes of decomposition of hydrogen peroxide in particular allows the development of interconnected pores of a typical dimension of 5-20 μm . This controlled pore generation is a key factor that affects the drug loading capacity and the drug release rate of microsphere and can be used to optimize microsphere performance based on therapeutic needs.

Vibrating Orifice Aerosol Generator Method

Vibrating orifice aerosol generator (VOAG) method is mainly used for producing lipid-bilayered mesoporous silica particles. The procedure starts with refluxing tetraethylorthosilicate, ethanol, water and dilute hydrochloric acid to prepare a stock solution. The precursor solution is then diluted in a solvent with surfactant resulting in the formation of monodisperse droplets by controlled vibration of the orifice. Uniform micro particles with increased stability and biocompatibility are obtained by encapsulating the generated microspheres in liposomes. The VOAG method is especially beneficial for products that must have a specific particle size distribution and surface quality.

Lyophilisation

To prepare porous microstructures through rapid solvent sublimation, freeze-drying process is used. This method is especially beneficial for the thermosensitive drugs, but it can sometimes lead to shrinking or cracking of the particles. [6]

Fig.5 Lyophilisation method.

Water-in-Oil-in-Water

Both hydrophilic and lipophilic drugs can be encapsulated by emulsion solvent diffusion technique. This method involves the formation of a primary water-in-oil emulsion followed by emulsification into an external aqueous phase containing PVA, resulting in a double emulsion. Solvent diffusion and evaporation lead to polymer solidification, resulting in porous microsponges with controlled and sustained drug release properties^[6]

Oil-in-Oil (O/O) Emulsion Solvent Diffusion

In this technique, the polymer solution is stirred into the non-aqueous external phase containing surfactant. Drug release properties of microsphere particles can be controlled by the diffusion of the solvent^[6]

COMPARATIVE OVERVIEW ^[31,32,33,34]

PARAMETER	MICROSPONGES	CONVENTIONAL DOSAGE FORM	OTHER NOVEL SYSTEM
Particle size	5-300 μm, porous microspheres	Macro (>1000 μm)	10-1000nm, often unilamellar or multilamellar
Drug release	Sustained / controlled via porous structure	Immediate or rapid, often burst effects	Targeted/ controlled, but pH/enzyme-sensitive
Loading capacity	High for hydrophilic/hydrophobic drugs	Limited for poorly soluble drugs	Moderate, lipid/polymer-based
Stability	Enhanced thermal/chemical stability	Prone to degradation, short shelf life	Good, but sensitive to light/ oxidation
Side effects	Reduced irritation, better patient compliance	Higher due to high initial dose	Variable, potential toxicity from carriers

Applications	Topical, oral, colon targeted	Topical/oral, broad but non specific	Systemic/ targeted
Formulation flexibility	High (gel, cream, powder)	Low, fixed forms	High, but complex manufacturing
Cost/complexity	Moderate, microsphere tech	Low cost, simple	High, advanced synthesis

Table no 1. Comparative overview

MECHANISM OF DRUG RELEASE FROM MICROSPONGES

The drug should not be too soluble in the vehicle used for its microsphere-based delivery. Vehicles therefore need to be carefully designed at the product development stage to produce controlled and sustained releases. This may be done by embedding the drug in the free form in a solvent with a moderate solubilizing power to get proper entrapment into the microsphere. The release process begins by the disruption of equilibrium between the polymer matrix and the carrier system, releasing an initial dose and allowing the entrapped drug to be gradually released.

The release rate depends on the partition coefficient between polymer and solvent, the surface area of the microsphere, the average pore size and environmental variables like moisture, pH, temperature, and external pressure. These factors combine to dictate the diffusion rate and extent of the drugs so that a controlled and sustained release profile can be achieved. ^[11] Fig 6

Fig.6 Drug substance release from microsphere at site of action^[11]

CHARACTERIZATION OF MICROSPONGES

Preformulation Studies

Preformulation is a series of investigations that are performed to predict the physicochemical properties of a new drug substance. These studies are important because they predict the behavior the drug will exhibit in the dosage form and establish the parameters that are critical

to the development of a dose form. They also give clues as to formulation strategies and stability issues. These initial evaluations, before the formulation design, are pictorialized in Fig. 10^[12,13,14]

Fig.7 Brief summary of preformulation studies^[11]

Particle Size

There are a number of formulation and processing parameters that may influence the particle size of microsp sponge formulations. Optical microscope with an ocular micrometer and stage micrometer or laser diffractometer can be used to measure the size of the loaded and unloaded microsponges. The results can be reported as mean size range. ^[9]

Analysis using Scanning Electron Microscopy.

The microsponges are studied with the help of scanning electron microscopy (SEM) regarding its morphology and surface characteristics. All the samples are coated with gold palladium alloy under vacuum. Coated samples are then examine using SEM analyzer. The dried samples are placed on NEM TAPE adhesive paper and photographed.^[15]

Production Yield

Production yield is calculated to know the efficiency of any method thus it helps in selection of appropriate method of production. After preparation of formulation practicle yield is calculated. It is the percentage of the total mass of product obtained from the total mass used which can be calculated from the following formula:

$$\text{The percentage yield} = \text{Practical yield} \times 100 / \text{Theoretical yield (drug + polymer)} \quad [16,17]$$

Drug release study

In-vitro dissolution and diffusion tests are typically used to assess the release of drugs from microsponges. In-vitro dissolution study is conducted in USP Dissolution Apparatus I or USP Dissolution Apparatus II at 37 ± 0.5 °C and samples are collected at predetermined time intervals for analysis by UV spectrophotometric or HPLC method to calculate cumulative percentage drug released. On understanding the release mechanism, the release data is fitted into the models like Zero order Kinetics, First order Kinetics, Higuchi model and

Korsmeyer–Peppas model. Also in-vitro diffusion studies can be performed using a Franz Diffusion Cell to determine the drug permeation through a given membrane. The drug cumulative permeated and flux are computed. Both of these studies validate the controlled release properties of microsp sponge formulations. [10, 35,36]

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)

The thermal study and compatibility of drug loaded Microsponges is carried out by DSC. The method is formulated by comparing thermograms of samples of pure drug, polymer, physical mixture and microsp sponge formulation on heating at a controlled rate, to observe melting points and thermal transitions. The reduction and/or shift of the melting endotherm peak in the microsp sponge formulation, compared with the pure drug, implies successful drug entrapment and possibly an amorphous or molecularly dispersed state of the drug. The presence of no other peaks means that the drug and polymer are compatible. Therefore, DSC verifies that the drugs have been incorporated and stable into the microsp sponge system. [37,38,39]

Encapsulation efficiency

The encapsulation efficiency (EE%) represents the percentage of the active pharmaceutical ingredient that was effectively encapsulated in the microsp sponge matrix. This value is found by dividing the measured amount of drug by the theoretical initial concentration. [11]

ACTUAL DRUG CONTENT – actual measured content in capsule

Zeta Potential

It is a measure of the surface charge on the particles and particle stability. If the value of zeta potential lies in between +30 or below -30 mV then the particles will not adhere to each other [20].

Zeta Size

A Zetasizer is used to determine the particle size distribution of the sample. The intensity distribution data of particles of various size range can be analyzed by using softwares and a graphical representation can be obtained. In results the peak on the graph indicates the size of most particles present in the sample.[20]

FTIR study

FTIR technique is used to investigate the drug-polymer interaction in formulation. Typically FTIR is done to check the compatibility of drug and polymer in the physical mixture of them and in the final formulation in a microsp sponge based drug delivery system. The characteristics absorption bands of drug are carefully examined and compared with spectra. Major peaks of the functional groups are retained in the physical mixture and in the final formulation, thus, no chemical interaction between drug and polymer exists. If new peaks appear or new characteristics bands disappear, the reverse is true – that is, incompatibility or chemical interaction may be indicated. Hence FTIR analysis is important to confirm drug stability in the process of formulation. [21]

Pore Volume and Pore Size Determination

To examine the size of nanocavities generated in MDS, a porosity analysis can be done. Pore structure, diameter, and volume can be calculated as per Eq. Porosity can be determined as

$$\text{Porosity (\%)} = \frac{\text{bulk volume} - \text{true volume}}{\text{true volume}} \times 100 \text{ [22]}$$

Resiliency

The viscoelastic characteristics of microsponges can be tailored to yield beadlets with varying firmness or softness, depending on the requirements of the final formulation. A higher degree of cross-linking generally reduces the rate of drug release. Therefore, the resiliency of microsponges will be systematically evaluated and fine-tuned, with particular attention to how release behavior changes over time as a function of cross-linking density. [3]

The use of microsponges in drug delivery.

The use of microsponges is being advocated in topical and controlled drug delivery systems due to their sustained release and stability. They are successfully used in formulations that include benzoyl peroxide in the treatment of acne, fluconazole and itraconazole in the treatment of fungal infections, hydroquinone for depigmentation, oxybenzone in sunscreens and aceclofenac in anti-inflammatory therapy. Conventional formulations are not as effective as microsphere systems regarding prolonged drug action, irritation, skin retention and patient compliance. [8]

Current developments in microsphere Research.

The literature of recent years shows that microsphere technology has been extensively developed for the controlled release of different drugs prepared by various techniques including quasi-emulsion solvent diffusion, emulsion solvent evaporation, oil-in-oil emulsification, w/o/w double emulsion and suspension polymerization. In particular, a variety of drugs have been successfully incorporated into microsphere systems for topical, ocular, oral and wound healing applications such as oxiconazole nitrate, nebivolol, nifedipine, acetazolamide, metronidazole, silver sulfadiazine, and hydroxyzine hydrochloride and miconazole nitrate. The studies reported increased entrapment efficiency, extended release times, higher skin retention, lesser irritation and better therapeutic efficacy than the conventional formulations. The porous structure and release control of the formulations were confirmed by characterization techniques such as SEM, FTIR, DSC, and in-vitro release studies. The results show that the system based on microsphere is a promising alternative to the sustained and targeted drug delivery in pharmaceutical applications. [10,40-46]

FUTURE PROSPECT

The attention of porous polymeric microsponges as advanced drug carrier for controlled and topical drug delivery gained a significant attention. The major developments planned for the future are focused on biodegradable and stimuli responsive microsponges with the capacity to release drugs with targeted and sustained release pattern. Polymeric materials like PLGA, chitosan and hyaluronic acid are being studied for biocompatibility and safety enhancement.

There are other areas that are being explored using microsp sponge systems, such as oral, ocular, transdermal, and tissue engineering applications. Recent progress has focused on inclusion of nanotechnology, smart polymers and a combination drug approach for improved therapeutic effectiveness and patient adherence. The pharmaceutical and cosmetic uses of microsp sponge technology may continue to increase in the future as further research is conducted on scale up methods, safety evaluation, and regulatory approval.

CONCLUSION

The drug controlled release and topical delivery properties of the porous polymeric microsponges are of great interest for using them as carrier because of their porous morphology, sustained release and the stability of the drug in the carrier. These systems can overcome many of the disadvantages of traditional topical formulations because they enhance the penetration of the skin, decrease irritation, and minimize systemic side effects. Different preparations and different characterization techniques have been proven to be appropriate for use as antifungal agents, for anti-acne and anti-inflammatory purposes and for cosmetic products. The literature and marketed products show that microsp sponge technology has great promise for future pharmaceutical and dermatological use.

REFERENCES

1. Liechty, W. B., Kryscio, D. R., Slaughter, B. V., & Peppas, N. A. (2010). Polymers for drug delivery systems. *Annual Review of Chemical and Biomolecular Engineering*, 1, 149–173.
2. Kaity, S., Maiti, S., Ghosh, A. K., Pal, D., Ghosh, A., & Banerjee, S. (2010). Microsponges: A novel strategy for drug delivery system. *Journal of Advanced Pharmaceutical Technology & Research*, 1(3), 283–290.
3. Kumar, S., Tyagi, L. K., & Singh, D. (2011). Microsp sponge delivery system (MDS): A unique technology for delivery of active ingredients. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*, 2(12), 3069–3080.
4. Peppas, N. A., & Langer, R. (1994). New challenges in biomaterials. *Science*, 263(5154), 1715–1720.
5. Uhrich, K. E., Cannizzaro, S. M., Langer, R. S., & Shakesheff, K. M. (1999). Polymeric systems for controlled drug release. *Chemical Reviews*, 99(11), 3181–3198.
6. Gidde, N. D., Karande, K. A., Jadhav, S. S., Mistry, R. S., Mhetre, P. A., & Joshi, S. D. (2021). Microsp sponge: An overview. *Journal of University of Shanghai for Science and Technology*.
7. Osborne, D. W., & Amann, A. H. (1998). Topical drug delivery formulations. *Dermatologic Therapy*, 6(4), 297–310.
8. Biswas, R., Saha, S., Chatterjee, C., & Ghosh, S. (2022). Microsponges: A promising approach for drug delivery. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*, 13(1), 42–49. [https://doi.org/10.13040/IJPSR.0975-8232.13\(1\).42-49](https://doi.org/10.13040/IJPSR.0975-8232.13(1).42-49)
9. Alburyhi, M. M., Yahya, T. A. A., Saif, A. A., & Noman, M. A. (2025). Formulation and evaluation of lornoxicam microsp sponge-based gel as a transdermal drug delivery system. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 14(11), 200–217.
10. Yadav, V., Jadhav, P., Dombé, S., Bodhe, A., & Salunkhe, P. (2017). Formulation and evaluation of microsp sponge gel for topical delivery of antifungal drug. *International Journal of Applied Pharmaceutics*, 9(4), 24–29.
11. Tomar, N., Pawar, N., & Bahmani, K. (2020). Review on microsp sponge leading microporous particulate technology with controlled release. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*, 11(11), 5360–5375. [https://doi.org/10.13040/IJPSR.0975-8232.11\(11\).5360-75](https://doi.org/10.13040/IJPSR.0975-8232.11(11).5360-75)
12. Patil, N. S., Tadavi, S. A., & Pawar, S. P. (2011). Research on formulation and evaluation of microsp sponge loaded topical gel of ritonavir. *International Journal of PharmTech Research*, 3, 133–137.

13. Chaurasia, G. (2016). A review on pharmaceutical preformulation studies in formulation and development of new drug molecules. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*, 7, 2313.
14. Desu, P. K., Vaishnavi, G., Divya, K., & Lakshmi, U. (2015). Pharmaceutical sciences. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2, 1399–1407.
15. Anderson, D. L., Cheng, C. H., & Nacht, S. (1994). Flow characteristics of loosely compacted macroporous microsp sponge polymeric systems. *Powder Technology*, 78, 15–18.
16. Aloorkar, N. H., Kulkarni, A. S., Ingale, D. J., & Patil, R. N. (2012). Microsponges as innovative drug delivery systems. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Nanotechnology*, 5(1), 1597–1606.
17. Khan, M. A., Bolton, S., & Kislalioglu, M. (1994). Optimization of process variables for preparation of ibuprofen coprecipitates with Eudragit S100. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*, 102(1–3), 185–192.
18. Yadav, P., & Nanda, S. (2014). Development and evaluation of microsp sponge loaded medicated topical formulations of acyclovir. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*, 5, 1395–1410.
19. Patel, N., Padia, N., Vadgama, N., Raval, M., & Sheth, N. (2016). Formulation and evaluation of microsp sponge gel for topical delivery of fluconazole for fungal therapy. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Investigation*, 46(3), 221–230.
20. Zaman, M., Qureshi, S., Sultana, K., Hanif, M., Mahmood, A., Shaheryar, Z. A., Gulzar, F., Barkat, K., & Abdel-Daim, M. M. (2016). Application of quasi-emulsification and modified double emulsification techniques for formulation of tacrolimus microsponges. *International Journal of Nanomedicine*, 11.
21. Pavani, V., Vinod, M., & Anantha, P. (2017). Design, formulation and in vitro evaluation of microsp sponge-based gel for topical delivery of ketoconazole. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*, 8(10), 4222–4229.
22. Tiwari, A., Tiwari, V., Palaria, B., Kumar, M., & Kaushik, D. (2022). Microsponges: A breakthrough tool in pharmaceutical research. *Future Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43094-022-00421-9>
23. Rahman, M., Almalki, W. H., Panda, S. K., Das, A. K., Alghamdi, S., Soni, K., et al. (2022). Therapeutic application of microsp sponge-based drug delivery systems. *Current Pharmaceutical Design*, 28(8), 595–608. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1381612828666220118121536>
24. Gangadharappa, H. V., Gupta, N. V., Prasad, M. S., & Shivakumar, H. G. (2013). Current trends in microsp sponge drug delivery system. *Current Drug Delivery*, 10(4), 453–465. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1567201811310040010>
25. Kumari, A., Jain, A., Hurkat, P., Verma, A., & Jain, S. K. (2016). Microsponges: A pioneering tool for biomedical applications. *Critical Reviews in Therapeutic Drug Carrier Systems*, 33(1), 77–105. <https://doi.org/10.1615/CritRevTherDrugCarrierSyst.v33i1.40>
26. Tiwari, A., Tiwari, V., Palaria, B., Kaushik, D., et al. (2022). Microsponges: A breakthrough tool in pharmaceutical research. *Future Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 8, 31.
27. Kaur, M., Rani, R., & Singh, A. P. (2024). Microsp sponge: A review. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics*, 14(6), 294–297.
28. Jelvehgari, M., Siah-Shadbad, M. R., Azarmi, S., Martin, G. P., & Nokhodchi, A. (2006). The microsp sponge delivery system of benzoyl peroxide: Preparation, characterization and release studies. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*, 308(1–2), 124–132.
29. Gangadharappa, H. V., Gupta, N. V., Prasad, M. S., & Shivakumar, H. G. (2013). Current trends in microsp sponge drug delivery system. *Current Drug Delivery*, 10(4), 453–465.
30. Nacht, S., & Kantz, M. (1990). The microsp sponge: A novel topical programmable delivery system. In D. W. Osborne & A. H. Amann (Eds.), *Topical drug delivery formulations* (pp. 299–325). Marcel Dekker.
31. Sheorey, D. S. (2021). Microsp sponge drug delivery system. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*, 12(9), 1–10.
32. Kumar, A., et al. (2017). A review on novel drug delivery system: Microsponges. *International Journal of Drug Development and Technology*, 7(4), 77–84.
33. Yadav, S., et al. (2023). Microsponges as drug delivery system: Past, present, and future perspectives. *Pharmaceutical Nanotechnology*, 11(2), 107–119. <https://doi.org/10.2174/2211738511666221216141051>
34. Sivaramakrishnan, S. M., et al. (2011). Microsponges: A novel strategy for drug delivery system. *Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 14(1), 58–65.
35. Jelvehgari, M., Siah-Shadbad, M. R., Azarmi, S., Martin, G. P., & Nokhodchi, A. (2006). The microsp sponge delivery system of benzoyl peroxide: Preparation, characterization and release studies. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*, 308(1–2), 124–132.

36. International Council for Harmonisation. (2003). *ICH Q1A(R2): Stability testing of new drug substances and products*. Geneva: ICH.
37. Jelvehgari, M., Siahi-Shadbad, M. R., Azarmi, S., Martin, G. P., & Nokhodchi, A. (2006). The microsp sponge delivery system of benzoyl peroxide: Preparation, characterization and release studies. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*, 308(1–2), 124–132.
38. Comoglu, T., Gonul, N., & Baykara, T. (2003). Preparation and in vitro evaluation of modified release microsp sponge formulation of diltiazem hydrochloride. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*, 258(1–2), 87–92.
39. Trotta, M., Zanetti, M., & Cavalli, R. (1999). Preparation and characterization of solid lipid nanoparticles containing caffeine. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*, 195(1–2), 79–88.
40. Pandit, A., et al. (2017). Nebivolol-loaded microsp sponge gel for healing of diabetic wound. *AAPS PharmSciTech*, 18(3), 846–854. <https://doi.org/10.1208/s12249-016-0574-3>
41. Maheshwari, R., Sharma, P., Tekade, M., et al. (2017). Microsp sponge embedded tablets for sustained delivery of nifedipine. *Pharmaceutical Nanotechnology*, 5(3), 192–202.
42. Obiedallah, M. M., Abdel-Mageed, A. M., & Elfaham, T. H. (2018). Ocular administration of acetazolamide microsponges in situ gel formulations. *Saudi Pharmaceutical Journal*, 26(7), 909–920.
43. Kumar, P. M., & Ghosh, A. (2015). Development and evaluation of metronidazole-loaded microsp sponge-based gel for superficial surgical wound infections. *Journal of Drug Delivery Science and Technology*, 30, 15–29.
44. Kumar, P. M., & Ghosh, A. (2017). Development and evaluation of silver sulfadiazine loaded microsp sponge-based gel for partial thickness burns. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 96, 243–254.
45. Rizkalla, Z. C. M., Aziz, R. L., & Soliman, I. I. (2011). In vitro and in vivo evaluation of hydroxyzine hydrochloride microsponges for topical delivery. *AAPS PharmSciTech*, 12(3), 989–1001.
46. Gulati, N., Tomar, N., & Nagaich, U. (2016). Miconazole microsponges based topical delivery system for diaper dermatitis. *Ars Pharmaceutica*, 57(2), 77–87. <https://doi.org/10.30827/ars.V57i2.4987>
47. Kshatriya, P. J., Shinde, J. V., & Chavan, R. S. (2020). A review on microsp sponge gel as topical drug delivery system. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics*, 10(6-s), 125–133.